

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH MORTALITY AFTER HIP FRACTURE SURGERY IN OLDER ADULTS

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Keywords

Intertrochanteric fractures,

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Systemic immune-inflammation index (SII),

Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR)

ABSTRACT

To evaluate the association of available perioperative biomarkers—hemoglobin (Hb), systemic immune-inflammation index (SII), and neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) with 90-day and 1-year mortality after hip fracture surgery in older adults. This retrospective study screened 156 patients aged ≥ 60 years who underwent surgical treatment for hip fracture at a tertiary hospital between January 2020 and June 2022. Patients were excluded if injury-to-admission time exceeded 72 hours, or if they had pathological fracture, polytrauma, concomitant additional fractures, non-operative management, hematologic disease affecting blood cell counts, or periprosthetic fracture. After exclusions, 111 patients were included. Hb, SII, and NLR were obtained from routine blood tests on preoperative day 1 and postoperative day 1. Mortality at 90 days and 1 year was analyzed in relation to age, ICU admission (yes/no), and biomarker values. The cohort comprised 73 women (65.8%) and 38 men (34.2%), with a mean age of 79.41 ± 9.48 years. Ninety-day mortality was 11.71% (13/111) and 1-year mortality was 24.32% (27/111). ICU admission was associated with both 90-day ($p=0.046$) and 1-year mortality ($p<0.001$). Non-survivors had lower preoperative Hb at both time points ($p<0.05$); lower postoperative Hb was also associated with 1-year mortality ($p<0.05$). Non-survivors were older, and preoperative SII was higher among non-survivors at 1 year ($p<0.005$). NLR (preoperative or postoperative) and postoperative SII were not significantly associated with mortality. In multivariable logistic regression, preoperative SII was not independently associated with 90-day or 1-year mortality, whereas ICU admission was independently associated with 1-year mortality. In older patients undergoing hip fracture surgery, advanced age, ICU admission, and lower Hb levels were associated with increased 90-day and 1-year mortality. Preoperative SII was associated with mortality in univariable analyses; however, it did not retain significance after multivariable adjustment and multiple-testing correction, and should be considered hypothesis-generating.

INTRODUCTION

As the global population ages, the number of osteoporotic hip fractures continues to rise. Worldwide, the annual number of hip fractures was approximately 1.6 million in the early 1990s and is projected to reach nearly 6 million by 2050¹. Age- and sex-standardized incidence rates have been reported to range from 95.1 to 315.9 per 100,000 individuals². Following a hip fracture, all-cause mortality remains substantial, with reported rates between 14.4% and 28.3%².

Multiple factors influence morbidity and mortality after hip fracture surgery. The most consistently reported risk factors include advanced age, male sex, a higher American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) score, neurological comorbidities, and longer time to surgery^{3,4}. In addition to these clinical variables, considerable effort has been devoted to identifying simple and practical indicators that may help predict short- and long-term postoperative mortality. In recent years, inflammatory indices derived from routine complete blood count testing—such as the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR), and systemic immune-inflammation index (SII)—have attracted increasing attention⁴⁻⁷. While some studies suggest that these parameters may be effective in predicting long-term mortality^{4,6} others have failed to demonstrate a significant association⁸. These biomarkers are inexpensive and easily calculated, which makes them appealing for prognostic assessment across various clinical settings. Indeed, NLR and SII have been reported to be useful in predicting mortality in conditions such as cancer, sepsis, and COVID-19 infection⁹⁻¹¹.

NLR and SII are ratio-based indices calculated from complete blood count components and reflect the systemic inflammatory status of the patient^{8,12}. Although numerous studies have examined the prognostic value of these markers for mortality prediction in different clinical scenarios, findings remain inconsistent in the setting of hip fractures. Therefore, the aim of this retrospective study was

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to investigate whether preoperative day-1 Hb, NLR, and SII are associated with postoperative 90-day and 1-year mortality in patients aged 60 years and older undergoing surgery for hip fracture.

METHODS

Study design and participants

This retrospective study included all consecutive patients aged ≥60 years who underwent surgical treatment for hip fracture at a tertiary referral hospital between January 2020 and June 2022. During the study period, 156 patients were screened. Patients were excluded if they presented later than 72 hours after injury, had a pathological fracture, polytrauma, concomitant additional fractures, fractures managed non-operatively, active hematologic malignancy or hematologic disorders affecting blood cell counts, or periprosthetic fractures. After applying the exclusion criteria, 111 patients were included in the final analysis.

Data collection and variables

Demographic characteristics, fracture type, anesthesia type, time from admission to surgery, and history of intensive care unit (ICU) stay were extracted from hospital records and analyzed for their association with mortality. Inflammatory biochemical and hematological markers obtained from routine blood tests at preoperative day 1 and postoperative day 1 were evaluated in relation to postoperative mortality. Specifically, Hb, NLR, and SII were assessed.

Outcomes

The primary outcomes were 90-day and 1-year postoperative mortality. The associations between mortality and inflammatory markers (Hb, NLR, and SII) were statistically examined.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using The jamovi project (2022) (Version 2.3) (Computer Software). Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. As continuous variables were not normally distributed, comparisons between two independent groups were performed using the Mann–Whitney U test, whereas paired comparisons were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test; when expected cell counts were low, Fisher’s exact test

was applied. P values for multiple biomarker comparisons were adjusted using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR-BH) method. Multivariable binary logistic regression models were constructed for 90-day and 1-year mortality using **age, ICU admission (yes/no), preoperative hemoglobin, and preoperative SII** as covariates; collinearity was assessed using VIF. Kaplan–Meier survival curves were compared between ICU and non-ICU groups using the log-rank (Mantel–Cox) test. A two-sided p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

FINDINGS

A total of 111 patients (73 women, 65.77%; 38 men, 34.23%) were included. The median age was 80 years (interquartile range- IQR, 15.00). The 90-day mortality rate was 11.71% (13/111), increasing to 24.32% (27/111) at 1 year; 14 additional deaths occurred between 3 months and 1 year.

Baseline characteristics are presented in Table 1. Associations between ICU admission and mortality are summarized in Table 2. ICU admission was associated with higher mortality at both time points (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the study population

Variable	Category	n (%)
Sex	Female	73 (65.77)
	Male	38 (34.23)
Side	Left	60 (54.05)
	Right	51 (45.95)
ICU admission	No	54 (48.65)
	Yes	57 (51.35)
Hypertension	No	53 (47.75)
	Yes	58 (52.25)
Diabetes mellitus	No	86 (77.48)
	Yes	25 (22.52)

Table 2. ICU admission and mortality at 90 days and 1 year

ICU admission	90-day survived n (%)	90-day died n (%)	p value	1-year survived n (%)	1-year died n (%)	p value
No	51 (94.4)	3 (5.6)	0.046	50 (92.6)	4 (7.4)	<0.001
Yes	47 (82.5)	10 (17.5)		34 (59.6)	23 (40.4)	

Mann-Whitney u test

Comparisons of continuous variables between survivors and non-survivors are shown in Tables 3 and 4. In non-survivors, age was higher and preoperative hemoglobin was lower (p=0.007) at 1 year (Tables 3-4). Preoperative SII was significantly higher in non-survivors at 1 year (p=0.029), whereas NLR was not significantly different. However, in multivariable logistic regression (ICU, age, preoperative Hb, and preoperative SII), preoperative SII was not independently associated with mortality, whereas ICU admission was independently associated with 1-year mortality. Postoperative hemoglobin was significantly lower in 1-year non-survivors (p=0.023).

Table 3. Comparison of laboratory parameters by 90-day mortality (median [IQR])

Variable	Non-survivors (n=13)	Survivors (n=98)	p (FDR-BH adjusted)
Age	88 (8.00)	80 (15.00)	0.059
Preoperative Hb	9.40 (2.10)	11.90 (2.47)	0.007
Postoperative Hb	9.40 (1.40)	10.10 (2.02)	0.453
Preoperative SII	1465 (1453.00)	938 (1232.75)	0.105
Postoperative SII	1110 (1167.00)	1489 (1304.00)	0.805
Preoperative NLR	4 (8.00)	5 (5.75)	0.453
Postoperative NLR	8 (6.30)	7 (7.00)	0.916

Mann-Whitney u test;

P values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR-BH) procedure.

Table 4. Comparison of laboratory parameters by 1-year mortality (median [IQR])

Variable	Non-survivors (n=27)	Survivors (n=84)	p (FDR-BH adjusted)
Age	85 (10.00)	79 (15.25)	0.010
Preoperative Hb	10.20 (2.90)	12.05 (2.40)	0.007
Postoperative Hb	9.40 (1.30)	10.30 (2.20)	0.023
Preoperative SII	1324 (2070.00)	841 (1205.00)	0.029
Postoperative SII	1595 (1507.50)	1483 (1226.50)	0.978
Preoperative NLR	5 (7.50)	4 (5.00)	0.158
Postoperative NLR	8 (8.50)	7 (6.00)	0.978

Mann-Whitney u test

P values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR-BH) procedure.

After adjustment (age, ICU admission, preoperative Hb, and preoperative SII), ICU admission was independently associated with 1-year mortality, whereas preoperative SII was not significant in either model. In the 90-day multivariable model, none of the covariates reached statistical significance (all p>0.05). For descriptive classification performance, a manually selected probability cut-off of 0.20 was used due to class imbalance; the 90-day and 1-year models showed acceptable discrimination (AUC=0.81 and 0.82, respectively). Kaplan–Meier curves stratified by ICU admission demonstrated significantly worse survival in the ICU group (log-rank p<0.0001).

Figure 1. Kaplan–Meier survival curves stratified by ICU admission (yes/no) after hip fracture surgery. Survival differed significantly between groups. Survival differed significantly between groups (log-rank $p < 0.0001$).

DISCUSSION

In this retrospective cohort of older patients undergoing surgery for hip fracture, we identified several factors associated with early and late postoperative mortality. Within the first 90 days, mortality was associated with advanced age and lower preoperative hemoglobin levels. At 1 year, mortality remained associated with older age, lower preoperative hemoglobin and higher preoperative SII, and additionally showed associations with lower postoperative hemoglobin. In contrast, we did not observe significant associations between mortality and the NLR or postoperative SII, which may be attributed to our specific inclusion criteria and the timing of blood sampling. Collectively, these findings indicate that anemia-related physiological reserve, intensive care requirement, and preoperative inflammatory burden may be clinically informative markers of mortality risk in this population.

SII is an accessible biomarker derived from routine complete blood count parameters and may capture the combined effects of neutrophilia, thrombocytosis, and lymphopenia as a proxy for systemic inflammation and immune dysregulation. Because SII is inexpensive, readily available, and reproducible, it is an attractive candidate for perioperative risk stratification, particularly in settings where more complex biomarkers are not feasible. Prior work has shown that inflammation-derived indices such as NLR and SII are associated with adverse outcomes in a range of clinical conditions, including

malignancy, sepsis, cardiovascular surgery, and COVID-19 infection^{9-11,13}. In hip fracture populations, evidence remains mixed: several studies report that NLR predicts short- and/or long-term mortality, whereas other reports fail to demonstrate a significant association^{4,5,8,14-17}. Our findings add to this literature by demonstrating significant associations between preoperative SII and both 90-day and 1-year mortality, while NLR was not significantly associated with mortality. One potential explanation is that SII may reflect a broader and more persistent inflammatory environment than NLR alone, whereas NLR may be more sensitive to transient perioperative stressors, timing of sampling, or perioperative interventions.

Advanced age was strongly associated with mortality in our cohort, consistent with prior studies demonstrating substantially higher mortality among older patients (e.g., >80 years) following hip fracture surgery¹⁴. Age likely reflects frailty, comorbidity burden, sarcopenia, and diminished cardiopulmonary reserve, which may amplify the effects of surgical stress, immobility, and postoperative complications.

Anemia is a biologically plausible and clinically actionable factor in hip fracture care. Multiple studies have consistently linked lower preoperative hemoglobin levels with increased postoperative mortality¹⁸⁻²⁰. Reduced oxygen-carrying capacity may limit tolerance to perioperative blood loss and contribute to myocardial ischemia or other adverse events, particularly in older patients with limited physiological reserve.

Notably, our finding that postoperative hemoglobin was associated with 1-year mortality suggests that perioperative hemoglobin dynamics may also carry prognostic value, supporting the concept that postoperative trajectories can inform longer-term risk assessment¹⁹. Low hemoglobin at presentation has also been associated with complications such as pneumonia, which may indirectly increase mortality risk²¹. Together, these observations emphasize the importance of careful perioperative hemoglobin monitoring and optimization within multidisciplinary geriatric hip fracture pathways. ICU admission was significantly associated with both 90-day and 1-year mortality in our cohort. ICU admission likely reflects acute illness severity, perioperative complications, and overall frailty rather than acting as a direct causal determinant. Nevertheless, this association is clinically meaningful because ICU requirement can be identified early and may prompt closer monitoring, multidisciplinary optimization, and individualized postoperative care. Similar observations have been reported in geriatric surgical cohorts, where ICU admission is linked to worse short- and long-term outcomes²². In our study, Kaplan–Meier curves stratified by ICU admission demonstrated a more pronounced early decline in survival among ICU-treated patients.

Sex was not associated with mortality in our cohort, despite prior reports indicating higher short-term mortality among men after hip fracture²³. This discrepancy may reflect differences in population characteristics, sample size, or care pathways. Likewise, the absence of significant associations for NLR and postoperative SII may be related to limited statistical power, variability in the inflammatory response, or unmeasured confounding (e.g., perioperative infection, nutritional status, or complications).

Limitations

This study has limitations inherent to its retrospective single-center design, including potential selection bias and missing or unmeasured confounders. The number of deaths—especially within 90 days—may have limited power to detect smaller effects for some biomarkers. The lack of a significant association for NLR in our cohort may be attributable to limited statistical power—particularly the small number of deaths within 90 days—together with variability in inflammatory responses and the timing of perioperative sampling. ICU admission was analyzed as a binary variable and may encompass heterogeneous clinical indications.

Importantly, perioperative transfusion data were not available, which represents a limitation as transfusion practices may act as a confounding factor in the association between hemoglobin levels and mortality. Finally, other inflammatory markers (e.g., CRP) and validated clinical risk scores were not incorporated.

CONCLUSIONS

Advanced age, ICU admission, and lower hemoglobin levels were associated with higher 90-day and/or 1-year mortality after hip fracture surgery. Preoperative SII showed an association with mortality in univariable analyses but did not remain significant after multivariable adjustment and multiple-testing correction. Prospective studies with larger samples and standardized measurement timing are warranted.

Conflicts of Interest Statement: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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